

The effects of stimulus rate on the brainstem auditory evoked potential

N.A. Shaw¹

Abstract

The effects of stimulus repetition rate on the four principal waves (I, II, III and IV) of the brainstem auditory evoked potential (BAEP) were studied in the rat. Twenty one BAEPs were recorded at rates between 1 and 100/s for each of 24 subjects. The use of extradural skull screw electrodes allowed the recording of a well defined waveform even at the fastest click rates. Between 1 and 100/s, the latency of wave I increased an average of 0.12 ms, the latency of wave II increased 0.23 ms, the latency of wave III increased 0.24 ms, and the latency of wave IV increased 0.35 ms. The maximum increase in latency occurred at lower click rates for all four waves. Beyond 50/s, latency increases had reached an asymptotic value and there was little additional change up to 100/s. Likewise, brainstem transmission time increased from 2.29 ms at 1/s to 2.50 ms at 20/s and then remained nearly constant up to 100/s. Paradoxically, the effects of stimulus rate on amplitudes were the opposite of those on the latencies. The amplitude of wave IV was the least susceptible and wave I was the most vulnerable. Waves II and III displayed an intermediate and near identical loss of amplitude. At faster rates of stimulation the amplitude of wave I was so reduced that it became difficult to recognise in some animals. The results are compared with previous findings on the effects of stimulus rate on the BAEP in both animals and humans, as well as on similarly far field potentials in the somatosensory system. Some inferences about the generation of the BAEP waveform are made and it is concluded that the electrogenesis of wave I is quite distinct from that of the more rostral components. Possible clinical applications of the data are proposed including the use of the BAEP for intraoperative monitoring, determination of the optimum stimulus rate in routine recordings and the possibility of detecting abnormalities in the BAEP which are revealed only at higher stimulus frequencies.

Key-words: Brainstem auditory evoked potential — rat — stimulus rate.

Introduction

It has been observed that while there is a surfeit of studies on the effects of stimulus repetition rate on the brainstem auditory evoked potential (BAEP) in humans, there is a dearth of such research in animals (3). This is surprising because, unlike humans where BAEPs must be recorded using scalp electrodes

with an inevitable loss of definition at faster click rates (4, 11), animal BAEPs can be recorded using extradural skull screw electrodes. This permits the recording of well preserved potentials even at very rapid rates of stimulation. Animal studies may therefore resolve many of the conflicting results obtained when using humans as subjects (12).

Since its discovery nearly two decades ago, the BAEP has found a useful role both clinically in the assessment of a variety of otoneurological disorders (2, 22) as well as in more basic

¹ Department of Physiology, School of Medicine, University of Auckland, Auckland 1, New Zealand.

research into auditory physiology (21). The BAEP consists of a series of high frequency vertex-positive components which arise in the acoustic nerve and the nuclei and pathways of the auditory brainstem. In most mammals, the BAEP is comprised of only four principal components (waves I, II, III and IV) in contrast to humans who have an extra major component (wave V). It is now believed that two waves (I and II) are generated within the human auditory nerve compared with just one in animals (21).

There are a number of reasons for quantifying the effects of stimulus rate on the BAEP. First, it has been claimed that variations in stimulus rate have been valuable in helping to determine the origins of subcortical potentials generated in the somatosensory system (1, 10, 26). Recording the BAEP at fast frequencies may therefore provide insights into the electrogenesis of other far field potentials. Second, in clinical practice, large numbers of responses often need to be averaged in order to obtain good quality waveforms (2). This is because the BAEP is generated at such a distance from its recording electrodes that its amplitudes are diminutive. It would be useful therefore to determine what is the optimum stimulus rate which will allow each recording to be completed in the minimum time without compromising the waveform. Third, it has been suggested that the BAEP may be able to detect abnormalities in the central auditory system which only become apparent at higher rates of stimulation (16). It is important therefore to classify what changes occur naturally to the waveform at faster frequencies. Finally, a significant role which has evolved for the BAEP is that of intraoperative monitoring during posterior fossa surgery such as for the resection of acoustic neuromas (13). Under these conditions, it is imperative to provide the surgeon with near instant feedback concerning the current integrity of the BAEP. The more rapidly the BAEP can be recorded without inducing gross distortions in the waveform, the quicker this information can be provided and with it the possibility of minimizing post-operative hearing loss.

In the present study, the changes which occur in the BAEP following discrete stimulus rate increases between 1 and 100/s were investigated using the rat as subject. No previous study, animal or human, has investigated the effects of click rate on the BAEP in such detail over this frequency range.

Methods

Subjects were 24 adult male rats (300-400 g). About one week prior to the experiment, each animal had a small stainless steel screw electrode inserted in the skull at the vertex, while under pentobarbital anaesthesia. The screw did not penetrate the dura. On the experimental day, each animal was again given an i.p. injection of pentobarbital (60 mg/kg). Recordings were made while the animal was under a moderate or surgical level of anaesthesia. This was determined by the absence of withdrawal and blink reflexes and the characteristic EEG pattern. A total of 21 BAEPs were recorded at the following stimulus repetition rates: 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 85, 90, 95 and 100/s.

BAEPs were recorded using a Medelec MS6. Stimuli were rarefaction clicks of 0.1 ms duration delivered unilaterally to either ear. The intensity of the clicks was 128 dB pe SPL. The active (vertex) electrode was referred to a needle inserted through the stimulated ear. Analysis time of the trace was 5 ms and sampling interval 10 μ s. Each potential was the average of 128 responses. Bandpass of the amplifiers was set to 100-3.2k Hz. Throughout the recording, a steady rectal temperature of 37.5 °C was maintained with a heat lamp.

Because the time to record the potentials was comparatively short, it was assumed that the animal remained in a stable neurophysiological state throughout. However, in a previous report describing how barbiturate anaesthesia could modify the rat BAEP, it was shown that in some animals there was a marked change in the most rostral of the four components of the BAEP (wave IV), including its virtual disappearance on some occasions (19).

This phenomenon was also observed in a number of animals in the present study. Therefore, subjects who did not have a well defined wave IV even at low rates of stimulation were discarded. The discarded animals were in addition to the 24 subjects eventually used in the analysis of the data.

Results

A representative example of a BAEP recorded from the rat is shown in Figure 1. In this, and in all further illustrations and analysis, the latencies of the four principal components (or waves) were calculated from the onset of the cochlear microphonic potential. Peak latencies were always determined from the most positive aspect of their waveform. Amplitudes of the waves were calculated using their immediate preceding negative trough as a baseline.

Some of the principal changes in BAEP morphology which occurred as a result of in-

Fig. 1. — A representative example of a brainstem auditory evoked potential (BAEP) recorded from a rat under a moderate level of barbiturate anaesthesia. The four principal components (waves I, II, III and IV) are identified with their actual latencies (ms) in parentheses. CM identifies the cochlear microphonic potential from which all latencies were calculated. The arrows indicate the preceding trough of negativity from which the amplitude of each wave was measured. The BAEP illustrated was recorded at a stimulus rate of 5/s.

creasing stimulus rate are shown in Figures 2-6. As click rates became more rapid, there was a concomitant increase in the latency of all four waves. However, it is apparent from all five examples in Figures 2-6 that this increase was not steadily incremental. The most significant increases occurred at the lower rates of stimulation. Beyond a rate of approximately 50/s, the increases in latency seemed to plateau out and there was often little or no additional change up to 100/s. Changes in amplitude with increasing stimulus rate seemed to be rather more linear than those of latency but some waves, especially wave IV, showed little or no rate-dependent diminution in energy (e.g. Figs. 2 and 5). The waveform which appeared to be most affected by increasing stimulus rate was wave I. Even at the highest stimulus rates employed, the three later waves were invariably well preserved and recognizable. In contrast, wave I appeared to be disproportionately reduced in amplitude (compare the recordings at 1 and 100/s in Figures 2, 3 and 4). In some animals, at the highest rates of stimulation, wave I had deteriorated so severely that it could be barely identified (Figs. 5 and 6).

It is also clear from several of the BAEP examples that wave IV is comprised of a cluster of subcomponents, one of which is the

Fig. 2. — The first of five examples illustrating the effects of stimulus frequency on the BAEP in the rat. In this and the following examples, BAEPs recorded at the eight different click rates indicated were selected from a possible total of twenty one. Latency values were calculated in the same manner as those in Figure 1.

Fig. 3. — A second example of the effects of stimulus frequency on the BAEP at selected click rates between 1 and 100/s.

Fig. 6. — A fifth example of the effects of stimulus rate on the BAEP.

Fig. 4. — A third example of the effects of stimulus rate on the BAEP.

Fig. 5. — A fourth example of the effects of stimulus rate on the BAEP.

dominant peak at a particular stimulus rate (Figs. 3, 4 and 6). The relatively large and abrupt increases which could occur over a relatively narrow frequency range were therefore probably due to the replacement of one subcomponent by a later one.

Group data for all 24 animals is summarised in Figures 7 and 8. Figure 7 displays the mean increases in latency as a function of stimulus rate. The rate/latency curves generated by the four waves were not however parallel and indicate that increases in stimulation had the most pronounced effect on wave IV. There was a lesser and similar overall effect on

Fig. 7. — Mean changes in the latency of the four BAEP waves following increases in stimulus rate from 1-100/s.

Fig. 8. — Mean changes in the amplitude of the four BAEP waves following increases in stimulus rate from 1-100/s. The data is expressed as a percentage of the amplitude recorded at a stimulus rate of 1/s. This was due to the interanimal variability in absolute amplitudes. Amplitudes were calculated in the manner described in Figure 1. Note that if values for different waves overlapped, one symbol was displaced just above or below the other in order to preserve clarity.

waves II and III and the least effect was on wave I. Between click rates of 1 and 100/s. there was an overall increase of 0.12 ms for wave I, 0.23 ms for wave II, 0.24 ms for wave III, and 0.35 ms for wave IV. However, the steeper part of the curves for all four waves seemed to be confined to stimulus rates in the range 1-50/s. After 50/s, increases in latency approached an asymptote and remained largely stable up to 100/s. These findings that the most marked changes in latency occurred at lower rates of stimulation confirm the trends shown in the individual examples (Figs. 2-6).

Figure 8 shows the mean loss in amplitude as a function of stimulus rate. The data was transformed into percentages using the 1/s recording as the baseline because of the inter-animal variability in absolute voltages. Initially there was a small temporary enhancement in amplitude as the stimulus rate

increased from 1 to 5/s. From 10/s onwards, there was a steady decrement in amplitude for waves I, II and III. In contrast, the decline in wave IV amplitude came to a halt at about 25/s and then remained nearly constant at approximately 80% of the baseline value. Such a pattern confirms the impression created in Figures 2-6 that wave IV seems relatively resistant to a rapid click rate. Paradoxically, the susceptibility of the amplitude of the four BAEP waves to stimulus rate changes was the opposite to that found for the latencies. Wave IV was the least vulnerable. The loss of amplitude was greater for waves II and III but overall decline in amplitude was less than 50%. As was the case for the latencies, the amplitude/rate slopes were very similar for waves II and III. The greatest rate-dependent change in amplitude occurred to wave I. With click rates faster than 30/s, wave I started to progressively separate itself from the later three. By 100/s, overall amplitude was just 25% of the baseline.

Brainstem transmission time (BSTT) is reputed to be the time for an afferent volley to traverse the brainstem auditory pathways (21). In both clinical and research contexts, it is one of the most widely used calculations involving the BAEP. BSTT is measured by subtracting the latency of the acoustic nerve response (wave I) from that of the most rostral of the principal components (wave IV). In the present study, mean BSTT at 1/s was found to be 2.29 ms, at 5/s it was 2.38 ms, at 10/s it was 2.42 ms, at 15/s it was 2.47 ms, and at 20/s it was 2.50 ms. Beyond 20/s, BSTT remained very constant with all values within the range 2.51-2.53 ms. This information can also be inferred from the data presented in Figure 7.

Discussion

Among the several studies of the effects of stimulus frequency on the BAEP, there is a broad consensus that latencies tend to increase, while amplitudes tend to decrease as a function of faster click rates. There is, however, contro-

versy concerning the more specific details of what changes occur to the individual waves. Such discrepancies might seem unexpected given that manipulation of the stimulus rate would seem a comparatively simple variable to adjust. Some of the conflicting results probably arose due to stimulus rate changes being studied over only a limited range or else only a few stimulus rate settings being studied over a much wider range. The present set of data are consistent with some of the previous findings, incompatible with others, while a number of changes observed in waveform morphology have not been previously described.

Various ways in which the BAEP latencies respond to increases in stimulus rate have now been reported in the literature. The most commonly observed pattern is one in which all waves are sensitive to a faster stimulus rate but with successive components showing a progressively greater increase than preceding ones. A corollary of this non-parallel pattern is that not only absolute latencies increase with a faster stimulus rate but also interpeak latencies including BSTT (16, 17). In some studies there appears to be a steady incremental increase in latency whereas in others there is a proportionately greater increase at faster click rates (6, 12). This type of rate-dependent latency change has been described for both man (6, 23, 25) and animals (3, 12). An alternative type of response is one in which the degree of latency change in the early peripheral waves is repeated in a basically unmodified manner in the more central rostral components. Such a uniform and parallel pattern of latency increase across all waves implies that BSTT and other relative latency measurements will be unaffected by the stimulus rate. This is a much less frequently reported pattern (8). Still other investigators have described how individual waves within the BAEP complex may remain invulnerable to faster rates while the remainder are susceptible. Sometimes the wave which is most immune to change is in the periphery (16), while in others it is reported to be the most central of the principal BAEP components (9).

The present set of results is most compatible

with the first pattern, but there were also significant differences. Wave II increased proportionately more than wave I over the frequency range studied, but its overall increase was almost identical to wave III. This is probably not what would have been predicted if a synapse interposed between the generation of waves II and III contributed an additional delay as stimulus rate increased. It is also notable that the bulk of the increase in latencies occurred, not at faster rates as might have been expected, but rather at the lower ones. It appears that once the sensory system has made an adjustment to more rapid stimulus rates, it can then accommodate much faster ones with little or no additional change in latency. Such a response does not appear to be unique to either the brainstem pathways or even the auditory system. For instance, in a previous study on the effects of stimulus rate on the cortical somatosensory evoked potential (SEP), these components also displayed a complex pattern of change not unlike that of the BAEP waves (20). Although SEPs were studied over a much narrower and lower frequency range of stimulus rates than for the BAEP, there was likewise little evidence of a steady incremental increase in latencies. A common assumption that there exists a simple linear relationship between increasing stimulus rate and the prolongation of evoked potential latencies may not therefore be correct for either cortical or subcortical activity.

The neural processes, and the site where they originate, which underlie the increases in latencies and other rate-dependent changes in waveform remain uncertain (4, 11, 18). There is agreement that a peripheral adaptation process probably operating at the cochlear hair cell-auditory nerve junction must be at least partially responsible (4). There is contention, however, whether it is also necessary to invoke a secondary and more central adaptation mechanism (3, 6, 18, 23, 24). Support for the former position is provided when changes in the peripheral component (wave I) are transferred with little or no alteration to successively higher levels. An example is the findings of Huang and Buchwald (8). Nonetheless, the weight of evi-

dence favours the latter position. The many reports of the increases in BSTT, including the present data, with faster click rates would seem to implicate a cumulative synaptic mechanism operating within the relay nuclei of the auditory brainstem. The behaviour of waves II and III described in the present study is not entirely consistent with this theory and therefore remains anomalous. Moreover, the ability of all four BAEP waves to tolerate high rates of stimulation with little apparent change in latency beyond an initial adjustment, suggests that the adaptation process, both peripherally and centrally, must be more intricate than sometimes assumed.

The effects of stimulus rate on BAEP amplitudes seem no less complex than those on latencies. Some studies have reported that faster click rates act uniformly on all the major BAEP waves in reducing their amplitudes (3, 8). Such a monotonic pattern would be consistent with the notion that the adaptation process is operating solely at the periphery of the sensory system. An alternative and more irregular pattern is one where the earliest wave of the BAEP is disproportionately reduced in amplitude, the intermediate waves display a variable loss of amplitude, while the latest wave of the principal components is also the most robust and least vulnerable to rate effects. Such a pattern is similar to the present findings and variations of it have been frequently described (9, 11, 12, 14, 18, 23, 25). These are rather opposite of the changes which occur in the somatosensory system where potentials generated in the spinal, brainstem and subcortical tracts display a much more predictable progressive decline in the amplitude of successive responses with increasing stimulus rate (1, 10, 26). This implies that the electrogenesis of the BAEP waves may be quite different from ostensibly similar far field activity generated in the somatosensory system.

The marked susceptibility of wave I amplitude to faster click rates most likely indicates that the aetiology of this potential is quite distinct from the later waves (21). Wave I is thought to reflect the compound action potential in the acoustic nerve whereas waves II, III

and IV may be generated by synaptic events which are apparently more resistant to rapid stimulation. Huang and Buchwald (7) have discovered that high frequency short latency units exist in the brainstem auditory nuclei and these may well underlie the generation of the more central BAEP waves. In this conception, therefore, the BAEP is not a homogeneous potential but rather a composite response with at least two different types of generator.

The majority of studies of click rate, including the present one, agree that wave IV (or wave V in humans) is simultaneously the most sensitive to latency increase while being the least susceptible to amplitude attenuation. It has also been observed in the present study and elsewhere (4) that wave IV does not seem to be a homogeneous potential but rather is an amalgam of activity from several subcomponents. It is probable that temporal dispersion of the afferent volley induced by the adaptation mechanisms underlies at least some of the changes which occur with increasing stimulus rate (4, 23). The individual subcomponents of wave IV may not, however, be equally sensitive to such desynchronisation thereby causing differential shifts in their latencies. This might result in dominant subcomponents being replaced by a previously minor one, thus accounting for the abrupt increases in peak latency often observed in wave IV (4). Associated with this would be the merging of subcomponents with the consequent summation or partial summation of their amplitudes. Such a process could compensate for the natural loss of amplitude at faster click rates and so create the impression that the original voltage of the waveform had been preserved relatively intact. In a previous study of stimulus rate and the cortical SEP, a somewhat similar phenomenon was also observed and basically the same explanation was offered (20). Such a theory could also account for instances where BAEP wave V (in humans) has been found to actually increase in amplitude with a more rapid stimulus rate (18).

While it is valid to extrapolate the results of evoked potential recordings from animals to humans, this must be done cautiously. Wave-

forms which appear homologous may not necessarily have identical generators. This may be less of a consideration for a comparatively simple and invariant waveform such as the BAEP than for cortical evoked potentials. Apart from the extra component arising in the human auditory nerve, there is a consensus that the generation of the BAEP is the same irrespective of species (21). Perhaps the major qualification in transferring animal data to humans is the earlier deterioration of the waveform which occurs when subcutaneous electrodes are employed. Despite this reservation, a number of findings from the present study might be applied to clinical settings.

First, there is the observation, not previously documented, that there does not seem to be a range of click rates at lower frequencies within which little or no modification to the BAEP waveform can occur. In other words, it is not possible to specify even a minimally fast stimulus rate which can be safely used without inducing at least some alterations to the waveform. Such a failure is in contrast to the cortical SEP in both man (15) and rat (20). It might have been predicted that a waveform would remain immutable at lower stimulus frequencies but demonstrate more pronounced changes at higher frequencies. With the BAEP a quite contrary pattern was found and marked increases in latency occurred with click rates as low as 5 and 10/s.

This makes the question of determining what is the optimum stimulus rate for recording good quality BAEPs in the minimum time, a difficult one to answer. In clinical practice, BAEPs are normally recorded at about 10/s (22). This must be considered a compromise choice and better defined waveforms may be obtained at lesser stimulus rates although at the expense of lengthier recording sessions. Such a conclusion is consistent with some of the earliest reports on the BAEP which suggested that the ideal click rate was not much more than 5/s (11). The 10/s recording rate does, however, have the advantage that it produces little apparent distortion in amplitude.

Increases in both absolute latencies and BSTT seemed to plateau out after the stimulus

rate reached 50/s. This finding may be relevant to the question of whether higher rates of stimulation are differentially sensitive at detecting abnormalities in the BAEP. This is a controversial problem with conflicting results (2, 5, 16). In a clinical context, therefore, latencies and interpeak latencies which did not remain constant within the 50-100/s stimulus rate range might well provide evidence of subtle nuclear abnormalities within the brainstem pathways (5, 16). Nevertheless, the consistent loss of amplitude at these higher rates may confound such recordings by making the more caudal waves difficult to recognise. Under these conditions, the best strategy might be to attend to just wave V (5).

One of the purposes in recording the present set of data while the animals were under a constant level of surgical anaesthesia was to allow the results to be more readily generalised to intraoperative monitoring. In retrospect, it does not appear that state of arousal or consciousness is a significant factor when click rate is examined in the BAEP. Huang and Buchwald (8) reached a similar conclusion. During intraoperative monitoring, what is of importance is not discrete increases in latency, but rather relatively gross alterations in the waveform, especially to waves I and V. Recording at too high a click rate with its concomitant danger of a loss or significant attenuation in wave I may easily create the erroneous impression that the acoustic nerve has been damaged or even destroyed by the surgical procedures. While wave V may remain intact, such a pattern could easily be misleading. The present set of data indicate that beyond a stimulus rate of 30/s, the amplitude of wave I begins to noticeably decline. This finding is therefore consistent with the recommendation that it is unwise to record the BAEP faster than 30/s during intraoperative monitoring procedures (13).

Acknowledgement

This study was supported by the Auckland Medical Research Foundation.

References

1. AREZZO, J., LEGATT, A.D. and VAUGHAN, H.G.: Topography and intracranial sources of somatosensory evoked potentials in the monkey. I. Early components. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 46: 155-172, 1979.
2. CHIAPPA, K.H.: *Evoked Potentials in Clinical Medicine*, Raven Press, New York, 1983.
3. CHURCH, M.W., WILLIAMS, H.L. and HOLLOWAY, J.A.: Brain-stem auditory evoked potentials in the rat: effects of gender, stimulus characteristics and ethanol sedation. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 59: 328-339, 1984.
4. DON, M., ALLEN, A.R. and STARR, A.: Effect of click rate on the latency of auditory brain stem responses in humans. *Ann. Otol. Rhinol. Laryngol.*, 86: 186-195, 1977.
5. GERLING, I.J. and FINITZO-HIEBER, T.: Auditory brainstem response with high stimulus rates in normal and patient populations. *Ann. Otol. Rhinol. Laryngol.*, 92: 119-123, 1983.
6. HARKINS, S.W., McEVOY, T.M. and SCOTT, M.L.: Effects of interstimulus interval on latency of the brainstem auditory evoked potential. *Int. J. Neurosci.*, 10: 7-14, 1979.
7. HUANG, C.-M. and BUCHWALD, J.S.: Interpretation of the vertex short-latency acoustic response: a study of single neurons in the brain stem. *Brain Res.*, 137: 291-303, 1977.
8. HUANG, C.-M. and BUCHWALD, J.S.: Factors that affect the amplitudes and latencies of the vertex short latency acoustic responses in the cat. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 44: 179-186, 1978.
9. HYDE, M.L., STEPHENS, S.D.G. and THORNTON, A.R.D.: Stimulus repetition rate and the early brainstem responses. *Br. J. Audiol.*, 10: 41-50, 1976.
10. IRAGUI-MADOZ, V.J. and WIEDERHOLT, W.C.: Far-field somatosensory evoked potentials in the cat: correlation with depth recording. *Ann. Neurol.*, 1: 569-574, 1977.
11. JEWETT, D.L. and WILLISTON, J.S.: Auditory-evoked far fields averaged from the scalp of humans. *Brain*, 94: 681-696, 1971.
12. MAIR, I.W.S., ELVERLAND, H.H. and LAUKLI, E.: Early auditory-evoked responses in the cat: rate effects. *Audiology*, 18: 265-278, 1979.
13. OJEMANN, R.G., LEVINE, R.A., MONTGOMERY, W.M. and MCGAFFIGAN, P.: Use of intraoperative auditory evoked potentials to preserve hearing in unilateral acoustic neuroma removal. *J. Neurosurg.*, 61: 938-948, 1984.
14. PICTON, T.W., HILLYARD, S.A., KRAUSZ, H.I. and GALAMBOS, R.: Human auditory evoked potentials. I. Evaluation of components. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 36: 179-190, 1974.
15. PRATT, H., POLITOSKE, D. and STARR, A.: Mechanically and electrically evoked somatosensory potentials in humans: effects of stimulus presentation rate. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 49: 240-249, 1980.
16. PRATT, H., BEN-DAVID, Y., PELED, R., PODOSHIN, L. and SCHARF, B.: Auditory brain stem evoked potentials: clinical promise of increasing stimulus rate. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 51: 80-90, 1981.
17. ROWE, M.J.: Normal variability of the brain-stem auditory evoked response in young and old adult subjects. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 44: 459-470, 1978.
18. SCOTT, M.L. and HARKINS, S.W.: Amplitude of the brainstem auditory evoked response: The effect of interstimulus interval. *Int. J. Neurosci.*, 8: 147-152, 1978.
19. SHAW, N.A.: The effect of pentobarbital on the auditory evoked response in the brainstem of the rat. *Neuropharmacology*, 25: 63-69, 1986.
20. SHAW, N.A.: The effect of stimulus rate on the cortical somatosensory evoked potential in the rat. *Electromyogr. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 27: 235-241, 1987.
21. SHAW, N.A.: The auditory evoked potential in the rat — a review. *Prog. Neurobiol.*, 31: 19-45, 1988.
22. SPEHLMANN, R.: *Evoked Potential Primer*. Butterworth, Boston, 1985.
23. SUZUKI, T., KOBAYASHI, K. and TAKAGI, N.: Effects of stimulus repetition rate on slow and fast components of auditory brain-stem responses. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 65: 150-156, 1986.
24. THORNTON, A.R.D. and COLEMAN, M.J.: The adaptation of cochlear and brainstem auditory evoked potentials in humans. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 39: 399-406, 1975.
25. VAN OLPHEN, A.F., RODENBURG, M. and VERWEY, C.: Influence of the stimulus repetition rate on brainstem-evoked responses in man. *Audiology*, 18: 388-394, 1979.
26. WIEDERHOLT, W.C. and IRAGUI-MADOZ, V.J.: Far field somatosensory potentials in the rat. *Electroenceph. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 42: 456-465, 1977.